

Review Article

A Review of the Impact of Jute Fiber Reinforcement on Mechanical Properties of Concrete

Salihu Sarki Ubayi¹, Dr. Esar Ahmad², Dr. Bashir Sabo Abubakar³, Shashivendra Dulawat⁴, Mustapha Nuhu Garko¹, Auwal Ahmad¹, Umar Shehu Ibrahim¹, Ibrahim Abdullahi Ibrahim¹

¹Postgraduate Student Civil (Structural Engineering) Mewar University, Rajasthan, India.

²Associate Professor Department of Civil Engineering, Mewar University, Rajasthan, India.

³Provost Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, P. M, B 3473, Kano State Nigeria.

⁴Assistant Professor Department of Civil Engineering, Mewar University, Rajasthan, India

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 06 July 2024

Keywords:

Natural Fiber, Treated Jute Fiber, Reinforced Concrete, Untreated Jute Fiber, Mechanical Properties.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.12670017

ABSTRACT

Natural fibers have historically been used also as the traditional building materials in Northern Nigeria, specifically in mud mortar for chocking, bedding, plastering, rendering, and block making. Globally, fibers like horsehair and straw were used in ancient construction, and asbestos fibers appeared in early 20th-century concrete. The 1950s saw the advent of composite materials, and by the 1960s, steel, glass, and synthetic fibers were common in concrete. Fiber incorporation reduces permeability, and leakage in concrete and increases economic sustainability. This study examines the affordability and effectiveness of using natural fibers, particularly jute, to reinforce concrete in developing countries. It reviews approximately 40 relevant papers on the mechanical properties of jute-reinforced concrete, summarizing almost 26 with author names, journal sources, methodologies, findings, and research gaps. The study analyzed and reviewed Experimental Papers for both treated and untreated Jute Fibers, Reviewed Papers on the same study, and other Research done with Partial Replacement of Cement or any of the Aggregates with Admixtures. Key findings among others, indicate that optimal results for jute fiber-reinforced concrete occur with a small percentage of jute fiber. Adding jute fiber improves mechanical strengths, such as compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength, but decreases the slump value as fiber content increases. This study highlights jute fiber's potential to enhance concrete's mechanical properties while providing a cost-effective and sustainable construction solution for developing nations. The study suggests the use of a superplasticizer in the concrete mix to enhance workability, and other works should be done for Mortar enhanced with Jute Fiber.

***Corresponding Author:** Salihu Sarki Ubayi

Address: Postgraduate Student Civil (Structural Engineering) Mewar University, Rajasthan, India

Email ✉: salihusarkiu@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Study Background

The most popular building material is concrete because of its affordability, durability, and compressive strength. (Yang, 2011) and (Neville, 2011). In contrast to compression mode, plain concrete is a heterogeneous composite material that is typically composed of cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, and water in the amounts prescribed by the specifications. It is also not able to withstand large tensile force. Research has been conducted on this significant shortcoming to create new building materials that increase the ductility of concrete. (Yan, 2013). Natural fibers strengthen concrete's tensile and impact resistance, reduce fatigue, cracking, and wear and tear, and enhance its ductility. (Mohammadi, 2008), (Yazici, 2007).

(A, Hossain, Anisha, & Tahmid, 2022), claimed that, creating durable, low-cost fiber-reinforced cement concrete has proven to be a technological difficulty in both developed and developing nations. Among the fibers used today are steel, carbon, plastics, glass, and natural fibers. In an effort to offset the natural scarcity of cementitious materials, natural fibers are more likely to be utilized as reinforcement. Numerous studies are being conducted to increase the ductility of concrete with the addition of various fiber types (such as glass, steel, jute, and fiber polymers). Fiber-reinforced concrete, or FRC (Fiber Reinforced Concrete), is regarded as one of the most promising building materials because of its increased ductility and decreased brittleness.

(S, Vishwanath, Prof, & H, 2017), opined that, the idea of using fibers as a material for reinforcement is not new; they have been utilized for reinforcement since antiquity. In the past, straw was used to make mud bricks and horsehair was utilized as mortar. Concrete was made with asbestos fibers in the early 1900s. Fiber-reinforced concrete was one of the hot subjects in the 1950s when the idea of composite materials first

emerged. Concrete mortar has extremely little resistance to breaking, very little ductility, and very poor tensile strength.

By controlling cracking caused by drying and plastic shrinkage, the addition of tiny, uniformly dispersed fibers acts as a crack arrester and significantly improves both static and dynamic characteristics. Additionally, they lessen the permeability of the concrete, which lessens water leaking. In concrete, some fiber kinds provide better resistance to impact, shear, abrasion, and shattering. The fiber materials may be made of glass, steel, carbon, synthetic, or natural materials. Steel fiber in particular is effective at boosting the toughness and compressive strength of concrete due to its high elastic modulus and stiffness. (Guler, 2019). But this fiber is prone to rusting. (Sun, 2021).

Moreover, Natural fiber increases the self-weight of the concrete and may cause a balling effect when mixing, which would make the concrete less workable. Similar to other varieties, natural fibers could enhance concrete's mechanical and other qualities. (Aluko, 2020); (Islam S. M., 2012). Architectural and decorative elements may also be present in natural FRC. For instance, pipelines, gas and water tanks, silos, corrugated roofing sheets, and reinforced concrete tiles are all made in African countries using sisal fibers. (Elsaid, 2011). Bio-fibers such as coir and kenaf were compared with polypropylene fibers in high-performance concrete to improve their durability properties, (Sivakumaresa, 2021).

The plant's bark is where fibers come from. The plant has the potential to grow up to 2.5 meters tall, with a base stem diameter of about 25 mm. The fully grown plants are first bundled and immersed in water. During this time, the organic bark completely broke down and the fibers were revealed. After that, the plant stem's fibers are removed, cleaned, and sun-dried. (Mansur, 1982). According to other research, jute may be used

efficiently in the production of safety helmets made from leftover polyester composites., (Subbiah, 2021). Jute fibers could be a cost-effective and sustainable construction material because they are biological engineering materials (Islam M. S., 2018). On the other hand, jute fiber has a tensile range of 250–300 MPa and weights around one-seventh that of steel fiber. (Kundu, 2012). (Ramaswamy, 1983), found considerably high tensile strength of the natural air-dried jute fiber.

Since ancient times, natural fibers have been utilized as reinforcement. In the past, mud bricks and mortar were made with both straw and horsehair. In the early 1900s, asbestos fibers were added to concrete. The 1950s saw the invention of composite materials, with fiber-reinforced concrete being one of the hottest subjects. There was an immediate need to find an asbestos replacement for the chemical in concrete and other building materials after the health risks associated with the material were identified. Concrete by the 1960s included steel, glass fiber, and synthetic fibers. Products using fiber reinforcement in concrete are being developed. (Boulekbache B, 2016). In addition, natural fibers are more widely available, more affordable, more rigid, and more recyclable than artificial fibers. (Hasan, Wang, & Mahmud, 2021). Because of their many advantages over synthetic plastics, such as their wide availability, biodegradability, lightweight, affordability, and ease of production, natural fiber-based bio-composites have virtually taken their place in several applications. (Ku H, 2011). Many researchers have suggested using a variety of natural fiber composites for a wide range of technical applications. (Hasan, Horváth, & Alpár, 2020); (Ahmad J, 2021); (V., 2020), and (Thanushan K, 2021).

(Ubayi, et al., 2024). Although modern building designs are still preferred, traditional building construction is easier and less expensive because

the materials used are primarily natural and local. Additionally, the craftsmanship involved does not require high-tech equipment and skills to process or install.

Consequently, to analyze the performance of concrete enhanced with jute fibers, one of the most effective natural fibers, (jute fiber) was chosen for this study, due to its impact as well as the low cost as stated above and the relevance of the literature read. And as a demand for sustainability is considered as a concept that addresses existing needs without hindering the development of the future. (Ubayi S. S., 2024).

In this paper, Relevant Literature was reviewed, on the Impact of Jute Fiber Reinforcement on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete, analyzed using the Qualitative Research Approach, presenting and analyzing the findings based on Differences in Mechanical Properties of Concrete with Jute and without the addition of Jute Fiber, Comparison between Concretes with Higher and Lower Jute Content/Percentage, how addition of Jute Fiber Decrease reduce workability of Concrete, Differences between Treated and Untreated Jute, Replacement of Cement with Admixtures, Replacement of Fine Aggregate with Admixtures, and Important Use of Jute Fiber as a Low-cost Building Material. This study investigates the issue that not everyone, particularly in developing nations, can purchase artificial fibers; natural fibers are sufficiently strong and inexpensive for this purpose. This is regarded as a fix for the issue at hand.

2.0 Literature Review:

This Article explores about 40 relevant topics from different journals and only 26 were summarized containing briefly the Author's Names, Journal, and Volume, the Title of the Paper, the Methodology used, the Findings, and Lastly the Research Gap of each Paper if any. The other remaining papers were read, understood, and further explained in the analysis.

2.1 Experimental Studies:

2.1.1 Studies of Untreated Jute Fibers:

- 1. (A, Hossain, Anisha, & Tahmid, 2022),** In the Malaysian Journal of Civil Engineering, Vol. 34:3 (2022), varying lengths of Jute Fiber (10mm and 15mm) were used in percentages of 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3%, with six cylinders for each sample, plus a normal concrete sample, totaling 42 cylinders. The mix proportion followed ACI 211.1-91, with a slump value of 75 and a W/C ratio of 0.4. The amount of concrete slump decreased with increased fiber content, and the highest compressive strength was observed at 0.1% fiber content for both jute fiber lengths. Compared to normal concrete, the compressive strength at 28 days increased by 64.34% and 70.9% for 10mm and 15mm fibers, respectively. However, longer fiber lengths (15mm) and higher contents led to a decrease in pressure strength. The study identified a gap, suggesting that the composite and fiber moisture-absorbing properties should be evaluated, and further experiments with admixtures should be conducted.
- 2. (Yaseen A, Nadia N, Muhammed F, Ahmed S, & Ektiffa S, 2019),** In the Civil Engineering Journal, Vol. 5, No. 4, April 2019, the topic "Concrete Beams Strengthened with Jute Fibers" explores the effects of jute fiber reinforcement on RC beams. The experiment tested 24 RC beams (150*150*1000mm) divided into four groups: three reference beams, three beams strengthened with a 15 cm wide carbon fiber strip (CFRP), nine beams strengthened with one layer of jute fiber strips (JFRP) of varying widths (5, 10, and 15 cm), and nine beams with double layers of jute fiber strips. The mix design aimed

for a compressive strength of 30 MPa with a w/c ratio of 0.54 and a slump test value of 75-100 mm, using a mixing ratio of 1:3 (1 kg hardener to 3 kg glue). Findings showed that increasing the width and thickness of JFRP improved the toughness, ultimate flexural strength, and load-carrying capacity of the beams, though ductility and stiffness decreased with wider strips. The load-carrying capacity benefited more from increased width than thickness, and the jute fibers enhanced the beams' toughness, improving resistance to seismic and dynamic loads.

- 3. (Khan, et al., 2023),** In the Journal of Buildings, Vol. 13, 1691, the topic; "Effects of Jute Fiber on Fresh and Hardened Characteristics of Concrete with Environmental Assessment," investigates the impact of jute fiber (JF) on concrete properties. JF was added at weight percentages of 0%, 0.10%, 0.25%, 0.50%, and 0.75%. Tests included compressive strength (CS), split tensile strength (STS), and flexural strength, using Design Expert 13 software and response surface methods. CS specimens (100*100*100mm) were fabricated according to ASTM C78/C78M, and STS specimens (100*200mm) followed ASTM C496 standards. The study found that incorporating JF decreases the environmental impact compared to other fibers, as shown by increased eco-strength efficiency (ESE). Optimal results were achieved with 0.10% JF, with no favorable effects observed beyond this percentage. The optimal slump occurred at 0% JF, while the minimum slump flow was recorded at 0.75% JF.
- 4. (Sahu & Tudu, 2020).** "Effect of Jute Fiber Orientation and Percentage on Strength of Jute Fiber Reinforced

Concrete," International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), investigates the impact of varying percentages of jute fiber (0.15%, 0.25%, 0.35%, 0.5%) on concrete strength. Tests, conducted according to IS code recommendations, measured compressive strength and modulus of rupture (MR) using PPC cement (53 grade with 25% fly ash) and M30 grade concrete. Specimens included 150mm x 150mm x 150mm cubes, 300mm x 150mm cylinders, 500mm x 100mm x 100mm beams, and 900mm x 150mm x 25mm slabs, tested at 7 and 28 days. Results indicated that jute fiber slightly altered compressive strength compared to plain cement concrete. The addition of jute fiber increased MR values, with a 0.25% continuous jute fiber addition enhancing MR by 15% in beams and 49% in slabs compared to plain cement concrete. Jute fiber reinforced concrete also improved flexural and tensile strength, suggesting its potential use in partition walls, door and window panels, and inclined roofs. Further analysis is recommended to explore jute fiber's application, behavior, durability, and chemical affinity in other contexts, considering different aspect ratios.

- 5. (Jack, Muhammad, Alireza, & D, 2023).** "Effects of Fiber Moisture Content on the Mechanical Properties of Jute Reinforced Compressed Earth Composites," *Construction and Building Materials*, Vol. 373 (2023) 130848, investigates the influence of jute fiber moisture content on the mechanical properties of Jute Fiber Reinforced Compressed Earth Composites (JRCECs). The study found that adding 0.5% jute fiber at natural moisture content increased tensile and compressive strength

by approximately three and two times, respectively, compared to unreinforced samples. However, a reduction in tensile strength was observed when jute fiber was saturated and subsequently dried. Regardless of moisture condition, jute fiber improved post-failure residual compressive strength and increased compressive and tensile splitting strength of compressed earth cylinders compared to unreinforced samples. Saturated and dried fibers exhibited reduced mechanical properties due to fiber degradation, swelling, contraction, and influence on optimum moisture content. JRCECs at natural moisture content exhibited the highest mean compressive and tensile splitting strength, outperforming both soaked and dried fiber composites and unreinforced samples. Contrastingly, another study indicated that wet jute fibers had a higher average tensile load than dry fibers, highlighting the need for further research.

- 6. (Mohammad & Syed, 2018).** This study "Influence of Jute Fiber on Concrete Properties," in the *Journal of Construction and Building Materials*, Vol. 189 (2018) 768–776, evaluated the effects of locally produced jute fibers (10 mm and 20 mm lengths) at volumes of 0.00%, 0.25%, 0.50%, and 1.00% on fresh and hardened concrete properties. Cylinder specimens were tested for compressive strength at 7, 28, and 90 days, and split tensile strength at 28 and 90 days, while beam specimens were assessed for flexural tensile strength at 28 days. The study found that increasing jute fiber volume decreased the slump of fresh concrete, with longer fibers causing a more significant reduction. Compressive strength increased with curing age and was

positively impacted by a small amount of jute fiber. Split tensile strength showed no significant influence from jute fiber content. Flexural strength was slightly higher for lower and higher jute fiber contents. However, jute fibers with an aspect ratio of 200 had an adverse effect on flexural strength. The study suggests a need for more research on the impact of jute fibers on concrete properties, particularly regarding strength development over curing age and the effects of smaller-sized fibers and chemical treatments.

7. **(Mohammad, Mashud, Md, & Islam, 2016).** In the journal of “Textiles and Clothing Sustainability, Vol. 2:11, an open access study by Springer explores the use of jute fiber for reinforcing concrete. The research meticulously maintained two mix ratios (cement/sand/brick chips by volume: 1:2:4 and 1:1.5:3) and water/cement ratios (by weight: 0.60 and 0.55). Various jute fiber lengths (10, 15, 20, and 25 mm) and contents (0, 0.1, 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75% by volume) were tested. Compressive, flexural, and tensile strengths were measured using cube (150 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm), prism (450 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm), and cylinder (150 mm × 300 mm) specimens, respectively. The study found that shorter fiber lengths (10 and 15 mm) and lower fiber contents (0.1 and 0.25%) significantly enhanced the mechanical properties of the concrete composites, with the tensile strength increasing by up to 35% compared to plain concrete. However, larger fiber lengths and higher contents led to balling, increased porosity, and degraded mechanical properties. The presence of jute fiber with
- more cement content further strengthened the concrete.
8. **(Khawaja A, Jamil, Syed, & Muhammad S, 2023).** In the Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Materials (2023), Vol. 32: 20220263, a study investigates the compressive and flexural behaviors of fiber-reinforced concrete using polypropylene, jute, and coir fibers. The concrete mix ratio used is 1:1.7:2.8, with coir fibers of 0.6 mm diameter and 50-70 mm length, comprising 0.5% of the concrete volume. Specimens include cylinders (150 mm × 300 mm) and beams (100 mm × 100 mm × 500 mm), with a constant water-to-binder ratio of 0.508. The study incorporates 80% steel and 20% polypropylene/jute fiber ropes (3 mm diameter) wrapped around 10 mm diameter steel bars. A total of 18 cylindrical and 36 beam specimens were cast and tested at 7, 14, and 28 days. Results show that fiber ropes with steel bars in coir concrete enhance both flexural and compressive strengths. The addition of fibers alters the cracking pattern in reinforced concrete beams, shifting it from end supports to mid-span. The rough surface of coir fiber provides a strong interfacial bond with the cement matrix, leading to higher compressive and flexural strengths in fiber-reinforced beams compared to control specimens. Cost analysis indicates that using jute and polypropylene fiber ropes wound on steel bars can reduce the cost of concrete steel-reinforced beams.
9. **(Lamees, 2018).** Wrote on the research article titled “Study of the Mechanical Properties of Jute Fiber Reinforced Cement Composites” published in the Engineering and Technology Journal, Volume 36, Part A, No. 12. The study

investigates the impact of jute fiber reinforcement on the mechanical properties of cement composites. Different fiber lengths (2cm and 4cm) were mixed into concrete samples with varying fiber percentages (0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% by weight of cement). The samples were tested for axial compression and splitting tensile strength. Results indicate that increasing fiber content and length slightly decreases compressive strength (4.3% - 12.3%), but significantly improves splitting tensile strength. The optimal combination was achieved with 1% fiber content and 5cm fiber length, resulting in a 19.4% increase in splitting tensile strength compared to reference concrete. The study highlights the potential use of jute fibers as a cost-effective material for construction applications such as wall panels and roofs.

10. **(Vivek, Abhishek, & Abhinav, 2021)**. In the *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology*, Vol.11, No.4, studied the behavior of jute fiber concrete (JFRC) including glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) rebars. They analyzed the compressive, flexural, and split tensile strengths of JFRC at 28 days for a mix design proportion of 1:2:3:0.60 with the addition of jute fibers. The study aimed to replace steel rebars with GFRP rebars in JFRC for pier applications to enhance performance, practicality, and durability. Results showed a decrease in compressive and split tensile strengths, possibly due to air gaps between jute fibers and other materials, but an increase in flexural strength due to the crack-arresting mechanism of jute fibers. Despite a decrease in the axial strength of prototype piers with GFRP reinforcement, the improved properties of JFRC favor its use

in structural applications like piers and load-bearing structures.

2.1.2 Studies on Treated Jute Fibers:

1. **(Lasiyal, Balot, Sharma, Falwaria, & Meena, 2016)**. In the *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, Volume 4, Issue 23, the study "Experimental Study of Concrete Additive Jute as Geotextile Material" investigates the use of modified jute fiber in concrete. Jute fiber was chemically and polymer-treated to activate its surface, reduce hydrophilicity, and prevent agglomeration, and then cut into pieces sized 2cm to 6cm. These fibers were mixed into concrete along with natural waste like coconut husk and wheat husk. The results showed that chemically treated jute fiber-reinforced cement concrete exhibited improved compressive strength. The use of jute fiber contributes to low-cost housing by reducing the need for cement and steel. Jute fibers are also beneficial in road pavement construction, erosion control, soil consolidation, and slope stabilization. As a geotextile, engineered jute fabric enhances soil behavior through separation, filtration, drainage, and reinforcement.
2. **(Islam, S. M., & G. M., 2023)**. "Using Jute Fiber to Improve Fresh and Hardened Properties of Concrete," *JOURNAL OF NATURAL FIBERS* 2023, VOL. 20, NO. 2, 2204452, investigates Jute Fiber Reinforced Concrete (JFRC) for compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, and plastic shrinkage cracking. The concrete mix, designed following ACI 211.1-91, included fiber proportions of 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, and 0.4%, with some fibers treated with NaOH solution. Fiber lengths of 20 mm and 25 mm were tested for their impact on JFRC properties and

shrinkage performance. Shrinkage tests on slab specimens (500 × 250 × 75 mm) were conducted under controlled conditions (40 ± 2°C, 60% RH) and analyzed using image processing. Results showed up to 61% reduction in crack area and 62% in maximum crack width. All mixes achieved a target slump range of 100-125 mm, with increased admixture demand as fiber volume increased. Compressive strength increased up to 7% at low fiber content (0.1-0.2%). The highest strength (25% increase) was observed with 0.4% fiber content for 25 mm fibers. Jute fibers effectively reduced shrinkage crack area and width, with 20 mm fibers reducing crack area by 18-61% and width by 62%. Treated fibers slightly reduced strength and were less effective in reducing crack area and width.

- 3. (MOHAMMAD, MD, & HAO, 2013).** "Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Jute Fiber Reinforced Composites", This study published in the Journal of Multifunctional Composites, investigates the impact of alkali treatment on the mechanical and thermal properties of jute fiber reinforced composites. Jute fibers were subjected to varying concentrations of NaOH solution to modify their surface properties, reducing their hydrophilic tendency and enhancing thermal stability by removing hemicellulose, lignin, and cellulosic constituents. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) were employed to analyze changes in fiber structure post-treatment. These treated fibers were then incorporated into polyester matrices to prepare composites, with mechanical properties such as flexural strength, compressive strength, modulus,

and strain at the break being evaluated. Results show that higher concentrations of alkali treatment (5-7% NaOH) led to superior mechanical properties, indicating improved compatibility between the fiber and matrix, resulting in enhanced interfacial adhesion and greater moisture resistance, ultimately suggesting avenues for further optimizing composite performance.

- 4. (Pruttipong, et al., 2014).** In the 11th Eco-Energy and Materials Science and Engineering (11th EMSES) conference, published in Elsevier - Energy Procedia, Vol. 56 (2014), a study on the effect of modified jute fiber on the mechanical properties of green rubber composite was presented. This research investigated the impact of varying jute fiber content (0, 10, 20, and 40 wt.%) in natural rubber (NR) composites on their mechanical properties. The composites were prepared using two roll mills and hot compression molding. The study found that increasing the fiber content enhanced the modulus and hardness but reduced the tensile strength of the composites. Additionally, untreated NR/jute composites showed better mechanical properties than treated ones, suggesting that fiber distribution plays a crucial role. The results indicated that cellulose fibers are effective reinforcements for NR matrices, with NR/jute treated with DPNR latex showing superior mechanical properties compared to those treated with HANR.
- ## 2.2 Review Papers:
- 1. (Ahmad, et al., 2022).** In the Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics, Volume 17: 1–17, the review "Performance of Concrete Reinforced with Jute Fibers (Natural Fibers)" summarizes the effects of

jute fibers (JTF) on the fresh properties, strength parameters, and durability characteristics of concrete. The review finds that while JTF improves the strength and durability of concrete, it reduces fluidity. Hot alkali treatment of JTF significantly enhances the bond between cement paste and fibers, improving mechanical and durability aspects. The maximum compressive strength, observed at 28 days with a 2% addition of JTF, is 20% higher than control concrete. Additionally, concrete's density, water absorption, dry shrinkage, and acid resistance improved with JTF. The review also suggests using a higher dose of plasticizer when incorporating higher doses of fibers.

2. **(S, Vishwanath, Prof, & H, 2017).** "Performance Evaluation and Strength Augmentation of Cement Mortar Reinforced with Treated Jute Fiber: A Review," *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, Vol. 6, Issue 7, July 2017, reviews the performance of cement mortar reinforced with treated jute fiber. The selected mortar mix has a constant 1:4 cement content, with fine aggregate (FA) replaced by manufactured sand (MS) in 20% increments up to a 0:100 ratio. Treated jute fibers with two aspect ratios were added in increments from 0.2% to 1%. Mortar cubes were prepared for each combination of FA and MS ratios and aspect ratios and subjected to water absorption, compressive strength, flexural strength, fire, and chemical attack tests. Panels were built for shear tests. Findings indicate that concrete mortar has low tensile strength, limited ductility, and little resistance to cracking. Adding small, closely spaced, uniformly

distributed fibers acts as a crack arrester, controlling cracking due to plastic and drying shrinkage, and significantly increases static and dynamic properties. Fibers also reduce concrete permeability, and bleeding, and improve impact, shear, abrasion, and shatter resistance.

3. **(Babu & Selvam, 2021),** Wrote a paper in the *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, the review paper titled; "Coconut and Jute Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites – A Review" Focuses on natural fiber composites reinforced with natural fibers. This paper provides an in-depth review of previous research on polymer composites based on coconut and jute fibers. The advantages of using natural fibers include high stiffness and strength-to-weight ratios compared to wood, concrete, and steel. The increasing interest in using natural fibers as reinforcements in plastics to replace conventional synthetic fibers has highlighted their potential. Researchers are particularly interested in manufacturing high-performance engineering materials from renewable resources, as these materials are environmentally friendly and do not pose health risks.
4. **(R, C, & B, 2019).** Wrote a paper titled; "Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Natural Fiber Composites - A Review", published in the journal *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials* by Springer. The methodology involves reviewing various studies on the dynamic mechanical (DM) properties of natural fiber composites (NFRCS) using techniques such as dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). The review highlights that natural fiber composites, including laminated, hybrid, and standard formats,

are effective alternatives to traditional materials, with hemp, sisal, jute, and other natural fibers serving as suitable reinforcement materials. DMA techniques, which assess phase variations under different frequencies and temperatures, reveal that the dynamic properties, including storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E''), and damping factor ($\tan \delta$), are significantly influenced by the temperature and the chemical treatment of the fibers. The study concludes that natural fiber composites are viable substitutes for synthetic fibers in dynamic mechanical applications due to their favorable DM properties.

5. **(Omar, Andrzej, Hans-Peter, & Mohini, 2012)**. This paper published in *Progress in Polymer Science*, Vol. 37 reviews the reinforcement of natural fibers in polymer composites from 2000 to 2010, excluding animal fibers, cotton, man-made cellulosic fibers, and wood fiber. The paper overviews popular natural fibers used in polymeric composite materials, examining their source, type, structure, composition, and mechanical properties. It discusses physical and chemical modification methods, such as corona and plasma treatments, and various chemical treatments to enhance fiber-matrix adhesion. The study also evaluates processing methods like thermoset compression molding and pultrusion, and their effects on mechanical properties such as tensile, flexural, and impact strength. Bio-composites have gained popularity due to their biodegradability, low cost, high specific strength, and renewable nature, especially in Europe. However, challenges like moisture absorption, inadequate toughness, and reduced long-

term stability for outdoor applications persist, necessitating further research on fiber processing, non-linear behavior, fiber-matrix adhesion, fiber dispersion, and composite manufacturing

6. **(Sureshkumar, Adithya, Gayathry, Jayasree, & Straya, 2022)**. The *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT)*, Volume 2, Issue 6, June 2022, presents a review paper on the strength and durability characteristics of natural fiber-reinforced cement composites with nano silica. This paper reviews the history, mechanical properties, and durability of concrete reinforced with various natural fibers such as hemp, pineapple, sisal, jute, palm, and bamboo, which are used as substitutes for synthetic, glass, and steel fibers. Findings indicate that natural fiber addition enhances crack resistance and reduces crack width, although it affects concrete workability. While compressive strength remains largely unchanged up to a certain fiber content, flexural and impact strengths significantly improve with the addition of natural fibers.
7. **(Ahmad, Ahmad, Dulawat, Ubayi, & Garko, 2024)**. In the *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, Volume 11, Issue 06, The paper explores the existing literature on the capability of Jute fibers as a viable and sustainable alternative to synthetic fibers in reinforcing concrete. This research highlights the benefits that jute fibers can provide, such as improving the compressive, tensile, and bending resistance of concrete. The results revealed that the flexural strength and tensile strength increased with the increase in jute

fiber length, while the workability of a fresh concrete mixture decreased. The fracture energy increased with the rise in jute fiber length. By incorporating jute fibers in concrete production, it is possible to reduce the reliance on synthetic fibers, which are non-biodegradable and can cause environmental harm. This approach aligns with the principles of sustainable development, as it promotes the use of natural and renewable resources.

2.3 Studies on Replacement of Cement and/or Aggregates with Admixtures:

1. **(ISHAN, ATUL, MUKESH, DR, & SUSANTA, 2022)**. The topic of the paper is "*Properties of Concrete with Jute Fiber Reinforced Concrete with Partial Replacement of Cement with Metakaolin*" published in the International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, Vol. 7 No. 4, April 2022. The methodology involves reviewing the impact of partial cement replacement with metakaolin and the incorporation of jute fibers on various concrete properties. The results indicate that replacing cement with metakaolin increases compressive strength while using marble powder reduces it but enhances it when used as a fine aggregate replacement. The addition of plastic waste aggregates yielded the highest compressive strength. Metakaolin reduced workability due to its fineness, and the inclusion of jute and nylon fibers further decreased workability. In terms of tensile strength, metakaolin substitution and the introduction of jute fibers increased tensile strength, with the highest tensile strength observed when metakaolin replaced cement, and marble powder was used as a fine aggregate. Lastly, metakaolin, with its high alumina
- and silica content, accelerated the setting time of cement.
2. **(J, Dr, Bifathima, & V, 2022)**. In the International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research, Volume 4, Issue 4, the topic of enhancing concrete performance through innovative approaches is discussed. With the understanding that building construction plays a pivotal role in global development, the study addresses the depletion of natural resources resulting from increased concrete usage. To mitigate this, the research explores substituting concrete proportions with alternative materials. Metakaolin is introduced as a partial substitute for cement across various percentages, aiming to preserve natural resources like fine aggregate. Additionally, moorum soil is investigated as a replacement for fine aggregate at varying degrees. To improve concrete's mechanical and lasting qualities, the study incorporates jute fibers into the concrete volume, enhancing its tensile strength. Test results suggest the largest 28-day strength improvement occurs with partial replacements in the 10-15% range, with the combined use of metakaolin contributing to increased strength parameters. This research offers insights into sustainable concrete practices, addressing resource conservation while enhancing concrete performance.
3. **(P & Hariharan, 2019)**. The project, published in the International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), explores the use of plastic jute fiber as an admixture and waste tire rubber as aggregate in concrete, aiming to address waste disposal issues and enhance concrete strength. Compressive and flexural strength tests were conducted on concrete

specimens with varying percentages of tire rubber and jute fiber. Results showed significant improvements in strength up to optimal percentages of both additives. Jute fibers demonstrated considerable enhancement in concrete properties, with a 23% increase in compressive strength observed. Cost analysis revealed an increase in cost with the addition of jute due to its extra expense. Concrete specimens with tire chips displayed improvements of 8% in compressive strength and 6.3% in flexural strength, with a decrease in cost attributed to tire waste utilization. The study concludes that using tire chips in construction offers a viable waste management solution and suggests potential applications for rubberized concrete in architectural and seismic damping contexts.

4. **(M, G, S, & I, 2020).** The study, published in the IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering 981 (2020) 032066, focuses on investigating the use of plastic waste as a partial replacement for fine aggregate in jute fiber-reinforced concrete (JFRC) to address environmental pollution concerns. By incorporating plastic waste, particularly PET plastic, into concrete, the research aims to mitigate environmental and health hazards associated with plastic waste disposal while enhancing concrete properties. The study explores various percentages of PET plastic waste replacement for fine aggregate, optimizing at 10% for mechanical properties. Additionally, jute fibers are introduced into the optimized plastic waste concrete at varying volume fractions to enhance split tensile and flexural strengths. The experimental results demonstrate that the mechanical properties of plastic waste

concrete improve with the addition of a 0.25% volume fraction of jute fiber. Moreover, the utilization of PET plastic and M sand aggregates in concrete reduces construction costs and promotes sustainable environments. The study concludes that the inclusion of jute fiber and plastic waste aggregates enhances overall concrete efficiency, with the optimized mixture offering optimal compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths. This approach not only reduces reliance on natural fine aggregate but also minimizes plastic waste accumulation in soil, thereby contributing to environmental sustainability.

5. **(J, Dr, Dr, & M, 2021).** *Experimental Investigation on Jute Fiber Concrete with Partial Replacement of Cement with Alccofine and Metakaolin Using M30 Grade of Concrete*, published in the INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN TECHNOLOGY, Volume 8 Issue 4, addresses the escalating construction activities and the environmental impact of concrete technology advancements. The study focuses on enhancing concrete strength properties by incorporating jute fibers and substituting Alccofine and Metakaolin for cement. Jute fibers are added to improve strength without environmental repercussions, with a 1% volume fraction used in the investigation. Cement is partially replaced with Metakaolin and Alccofine at varying percentages, ranging from 0.3% to 1.5%. Mechanical properties are evaluated, revealing that the addition of jute fibers and partial replacement of Alccofine-1203 (1.2%) and Metakaolin (12%) significantly enhance compressive and split tensile

strengths, with maximum values observed at 28 days. However, a combination of 18% Metakaolin, 1.5% Alccofine, and 1%

jute fibers results in decreased tensile and compressive strengths.

Table 1. Summary of Methodology, Test, and Results of Some Papers Studied

S/ N	Author(s)	Sample Type	% Jute	Length of Jute	Treated Jute	Untreated Jute	Slump	Results
1.	(Yaseen A, Nadia N, Muhammed F, Ahmed S, & Ektiffa S, 2019)	24 RC Beams	—	5, 10, and 15 cm	—	✓	Dec.	Toughness, ultimate flexural strength, & load carrying capacity increased while Ductility & stiffness decreased.
2.	(A, Hossain, Anisha, & Tahmid, 2022)	42 Cylinders	0.1, 0.2, & 0.3%,	10 and 15 cm	—	✓	Dec.	The highest compressive strength was observed at 0.1%, at 28 days by 64.34% & 70.9% for 10mm and 15mm.
3.	(Khan, et al., 2023)	Design Expert (version 13) software was used.	0%, 0.10%, 0.25%, 0.50%, & 0.75%.	100 mm in length, 100 mm in height, & 100 mm in width. And also, 100 mm in width & 200 mm in height	—	✓	Dec.	0.10% JF has been determined to be conducive to enhancing the CS, STS, and FS by 6.77%, 6.91%, and 9.63%, respectively.
4.	(Mohammad, Mashud, Md, & Islam, 2016)	Cubes (150mm×150mm×150mm); Prisms (450mm×10mm×150mm); & Cylinders (150mm×300mm)	0,0.1,0.25, 0.50, & 0.75 %	10, 15, 20, and 25 mm)	—	✓	Dec.	The large cut length and higher content of jute fiber result in the unfortunate tendency of balling formation and high porosity of composites followed by the degrading of mechanical properties of JFRCC about plain concrete. It was also noted that all the remarkable increment values were found mostly in the presence of higher cement content.
5.	(Lasiyal, Balot, Sharma, Falwaria, & Meena, 2016)	3 Cubes	—	2, 3, 4, 5 & 6 cm	✓	—	Dec.	Chemically treated jute fiber reinforced cement concrete exhibited improved compressive strength.
6.	(MOHAMMAD, MD, & HAO, 2013)	—	5 & 7%	—	✓	—	Dec.	The thermal & mechanical properties of treated fibers were superior to the untreated fibers.
7.	(Jack, Muhammad, Alireza, & D, 2023)	10 samples per test variable, I.e. A sample of 20 BFBs.	0.5%	20 and 80 mm	—	✓	—	Soaking and drying jute fiber causes a reduction in the mechanical properties of the fiber and the JRCEC. Also, jute fibers at natural moisture content should be incorporated in JRCECs to achieve optimum

								compressive and tensile strength.
8.	(Islam, S. M., & G. M., 2023)	Fibers were designated J20 and J25. Slab mold measuring 500 × 250 × 75 mm.	0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, & 0.4%	20 and 25-mm	✓	—	Dec.	Compressive and splitting tensile strengths improved by 7% and 25%, respectively. Furthermore, the bio-fiber had a significant influence on shrinkage crack control. In a controlled environment, up to 61% crack area and 62% maximum crack width reduction were achieved. Overall, jute fiber was found to be a sustainable biomaterial for concrete construction in an arid region.
9.	(Vivek, Abhishek, & Abhinav, 2021)	Replacement of Coarse Aggr. with Glass & Jute	5%	45 mm	—	✓		Compressive strength and split tensile of the JFRC specimen are decreased but flexural strength is increased as compared to normal concrete but the axial strength of the prototype pier including glass fiber reinforcement is decreased
10.	(Pramodini Sahu, 2020)	72 Nos. of cubes, cylinders, beams and slabs each are casted.	0.15%, 0.2%, 5%, 0.35 & 0.50%	2 and 3 cm	—	✓	Dec.	The addition of jute fiber enhances the flexural strength and hence the tensile strength. So, jute fiber reinforced concrete can be used as partition walls, door and window panels, inclined roofs, etc.

Table 2. Summary of Mechanical Properties of Some Papers Studied:

S/N.	Reference	Optimum Perc. (%)	Compressive Str.	Flexural Str.	Tensile Str.	Split Tensile.
1.	(Ahmad, et al., 2022)	0.1%	10.53%	6.25%	10.71%	—
2.	(Islam, S. M., & G. M., 2023)	0.1%	7%	—	—	25%
3.	(Mohammad, Mashud, Md, & Islam, 2016)	0.1%	15%	22%	35%	—
4.	(Lamees, 2018)	0.1%	12.3%	—	—	19.4%
5.	(Khan, et al., 2023)	0.1%	6.77%	9.63%	—	6.91%
6.	(A, Hossain, Anisha, & Tahmid, 2022)	0.1%	70.9%	—	—	—
7.	(Khawaja A, Jamil, Syed, & Muhammad S, 2023)	0.5%	13.82%	20.44%	—	—
8.	(MOHAMMAD, MD, & HAO, 2013)	0.5%	19%	39.63%	—	—
9.	(Jack, Muhammad, Alireza, & D, 2023)	0.5	84%	—	—	200%

Table 3. Chemical Composition and Constituents of Jute Fiber. (Khan, et al., 2023) *and* (Ahmad, et al., 2022)

S/No.	Constituents / Characteristics	Percentage (%) Jute Fiber
1.	Cellulose	60.00 – 72.00

2.	Lignin	12.00 – 13.00
3.	Crystallinity %	60-65
4.	Hemicellulose	22.00
5.	Fatty and Waxy Matter	1.00
6.	Nitrogenous Matter (as Protein)	1.00
7.	Miscellaneous	3.00
8.	Mineral Matter (ash)	1.00

Table 4. Physical Properties of Jute Fiber, (Ahmad, et al., 2022).

1.	Specific Gravity (kg/m ³)	1460
2.	Specific Modulus (Gpa-cm ³ /g)	20.4
3.	Specific Strength (Mpa-cm ³ /g)	306-592
4.	Young's Modulus (GPA)	26.5, 13-22.4
5.	Density (g/cm ³)	1.3, 1.3-1.45
6.	Elongation at Breaking Point (%)	1.5-1.8, 7-8
7.	Water Absorption (%)	13
8.	Tensile Strength (MPa)	400-800, 393-773, 350-550

3.1 Discussion of Results:

Optimal results for concrete mixed with jute fiber (JF) are achieved with a small percentage of JF, as higher amounts do not favorably impact the fresh and hardened features of the concrete. The addition of JF notably enhances the flexural and tensile strengths, although this improvement is contingent on fiber volume and length, with maximum amounts leading to a reduction in flexural strength. Chemically treated JF in cement concrete also shows improved compressive strength, with the highest compressive strength observed at the lowest fiber content.

Mechanical strengths such as compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths are improved with the addition of jute textile fibers (JTF). However, the value of slump decreases with increased fiber content, more so with longer fibers, indicating reduced workability. Jute fibers enhance the strength and durability aspects but reduce the fluidity of the concrete due to their larger surface area, which increases the concrete's harshness. Incrementing JF content leads to decreased workability, and the optimal performance is achieved with smaller fiber percentages.

Alkali-treated JTFs result in considerable improvement in the bond between the cement

paste and fibers, enhancing the mechanical and durability aspects of concrete. Alkali-treated fiber composites exhibit higher flexural properties compared to untreated samples, with superior properties observed at higher treatment concentrations. This improvement is due to the removal of moisture-attracting constituents from the fibers, which enhances compatibility with the matrix and results in superior mechanical properties. The addition of metakaolin as a partial replacement for cement increases compressive and tensile strengths at optimal percentages but reduces workability. Metakaolin accelerates the setting time of concrete due to its high alumina and silica content. Partial replacement of cement with marble powder reduces compressive strength, whereas replacing fine aggregates with marble dust increases it. The combined use of metakaolin and marble powder achieves maximum split tensile strength, indicating the potential for enhanced mechanical properties with specific mix designs. Table 1, shows the Summary of Methodology, Tests, and Results of Some Papers Studied in this article, it shows that various and different Samples were used with varying percentage dosages. The Highest compressive strength was observed at a smaller percentage of

jute. The chemically treated jute fiber reinforced cement concrete exhibited improved compressive strength, Thermal & mechanical properties of treated fibers were superior to the untreated fibers. Soaking and drying jute fiber causes a reduction in the mechanical properties of the fiber. In a nutshell, the Compressive strength and split tensile of the JFRC specimen are decreased but flexural strength is increased as compared to normal concrete but the axial strength of the prototype pier including glass fiber reinforcement is decreased. The addition of jute fiber enhances the flexural strength and hence the tensile strength.

While Table 2, shows the Summary of Mechanical Properties of Some Papers Studied, at least 9 papers only, to show the differences in Mechanical properties of Concrete enhanced with Jute fiber.

Table 3, consists of the Chemical Composition and Constituents of Jute Fiber studied in the article, (Khan, et al., 2023) and (Ahmad, et al., 2022). Lastly, Table 4, showed the Physical Properties of Jute Fiber, (Ahmad, et al., 2022), as studied also in the paper.

3.2 Optimal Results and Flexural/Tensile Strength:

1. Optimal results are achieved with small percentages of JF.
2. JF enhances flexural and tensile strengths, though high amounts reduce flexural strength.
3. Chemically treated JF shows improved compressive strength, with the highest compressive strength at the lowest fiber content.

3.3 Mechanical Strengths and Workability:

1. The addition of JTF improves compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths.
2. Increased fiber content reduces slump and workability, especially with longer fibers.
3. JF enhances strength and durability but decreases concrete fluidity due to a larger surface area.

3.4 Alkali Treatment and Mechanical Properties:

1. Alkali-treated JTF improves the bond with cement, enhancing mechanical and durability aspects.
2. Higher treatment concentrations lead to better flexural properties.
3. Removing moisture-attracting constituents from fibers enhances compatibility and mechanical properties.

3.5 Metakaolin and Marble Powder Effects:

1. Metakaolin increases compressive and tensile strengths at optimal percentages but reduces workability.
2. Accelerates concrete setting time.
3. Marble powder replacement for fine aggregates increases compressive strength.
4. Combined use of metakaolin and marble powder maximizes split tensile strength.

3.6 Important Use of Jute Fiber as a Low-cost Building Material:

1. Jute helps in making low-cost houses. Reduction in use of cement and steel by using jute as a replacement.
2. Jute is also used in the construction of road pavement, used for control of erosion, consolidation of soil, and stabilization of slopes (embankments).
3. The engineered fabric improves soil behavior through separation, filtration, drainage, and reinforcement.
4. So, this jute fiber reinforced concrete can be used as partition walls, door and window panels, inclined roofs etc.

4.1 Summary of Findings:

The slump of fresh concrete decreases with increased jute fiber content, with a more significant reduction for mixtures with longer fibers. Compressive strength improves with curing age, and small amounts of jute fiber positively affect this strength. However, jute fibers show no significant impact on split tensile strength over

time. Tensile strength is slightly higher for concrete with lower and higher jute fiber content compared to no fiber or the highest fiber content. Jute fibers with an aspect ratio of 200 negatively affect flexural strength, and their impact on split tensile strength is more notable at 28 days than at 90 days. In terms of flexural tensile strength, fiber length and volume play significant roles, with fiber volume contributing moderately and fiber length minimally. The inclusion of jute fibers reduces the number and width of cracks in concrete, preventing complete failure of the specimens.

Table 1 shows the Summary of Methodology, Tests, and Results of Some Papers Studied in this article, it shows that various and different Samples were used with varying percentage dosages. Table 2 shows the Summary of Mechanical Properties of Some Papers Studied, at least 9 papers only, to show the differences in Mechanical properties of Concrete enhanced with Jute fiber. Tables 3 and 4 show the Chemical Composition and the Physical Properties of Jute Fiber, by, (Khan, et al., 2023), (Ahmad, et al., 2022) and (Ahmad, et al., 2022) respectively.

5.1 CONCLUSION:

Natural Fibers have been used until today in the Traditional Building of Northern Nigeria as Building Materials in Mud Mortar for chinking, Bedding, Plastering, and Rendering and in the making of Blocks. They have been used as reinforcement since prehistoric times in other countries. Horsehair and straw were both formerly used in mortar and mud bricks. Asbestos fibers were used in concrete in the early 1900s. Composite materials were invented in the 1950s, and fiber-reinforced concrete was one of the hottest topics. By the 1960s, steel, glass fiber, and synthetic fibers were all used in concrete.

This study investigates the issue that not everyone, particularly in developing nations, can purchase artificial fibers; natural fibers are sufficiently strong and inexpensive for this purpose. In this

paper, about 40 Relevant papers were reviewed, on the Performance of Concrete Enhanced with Jute Fiber, effects of width and thickness, and percentage variations of Jute analyzed based on the mechanical properties of concrete reinforced with Jute fibers using the Qualitative Research Approach, only 21 that 40 amongst were summarized in tabular form of Rows and Columns, while the remaining were read and understood, The present study is conducted to investigate the Performance of Concrete Enhanced with Jute Fibers of different lengths, Width, thickness, and different percentage dosages of mixes on the mechanical properties of reinforced concrete beams, Cubes, Prisms, and Cylinders.

Fibers eliminate the unexpected failure that is common in plain concrete beams. Stiffness, torsional strength, ductility, rotational capacity, and the number of cracks with smaller crack widths are all improved. When compared to non-reinforced concrete, fiber-reinforced concrete has a higher tensile strength. It improves the concrete's long-term resilience. It slows the spread of cracks and improves impact resistance. By replacing Metakaolin with cement and adding jute fibers to the mix, the strength of concrete can be increased. Jute fibers are used in concrete to increase strength while having no negative impact on the environment.

Table 1, shows the Summary of Methodology, Tests, and Results of Some Papers Studied in this article, it shows that various and different Samples were used with varying percentage dosages. Table 2, shows the Summary of Mechanical Properties of Some Papers Studied, at least 9 papers only, to show the differences in Mechanical properties of Concrete enhanced with Jute fiber. Also, Table 3, consists of the Chemical Composition and Constituents of Jute Fiber studied in the article, (Khan, et al., 2023) and (Ahmad, et al., 2022). Lastly, Table 4, showed the Physical Properties of

Jute Fiber, (Ahmad, et al., 2022), as studied also in the paper.

5.2 Suggestions:

1. More work should be done on the impact of jute fibers on Mortar, as mortar can be used for chocking, bedding and plastering.
2. Moreover, a further experiment on jute fiber with an admixture can be carried out.
3. The use of a Superplasticizer in concrete mixed with Jute should be done to enhance workability.

REFERENCES

1. A, Z. A., Hossain, A., Anisha, A., & Tahmid, A. (2022). PERFORMANCE OF JUTE FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE IN THE CONTEXT OF BANGLADESGH. *Malaysian Journal*, 25-35.
2. Ahmad J, Z. O. (2021). Mechanical and durability characteristics of sustainable coconut fibers reinforced concrete with incorporation of marble powder. *Mater Res Express* 2021; 8:, 075505.
3. Ahmad, A., Ahmad, D. E., Dulawat, S., Ubayi, S. S., & Garko, M. N. (2024). Analyzing the Performance of Concrete Reinforced with Untreated Jute Fiber: A Review. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*. Volume 11 Issue 6. www.Jetir.org (ISSN-2349-5162), 09-18.
4. Ahmad, J., Arbili, M. M., Majdi, A., Althoey, F., Deifalla, A. F., & Rahmawati, C. (2022). Performance of concrete reinforced with jute fibers (natural fibers): A review. *journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, 1-17.
5. Aluko, O. G. (2020). A review of properties of bio-fibrous concrete. *Construction and Building Materials* 260:119671. Elsevier Ltd. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.119671.
6. Babu, B., & Selvam, V. (2021). COCONUT AND JUTE FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES – A REVIEW. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research - VOLUME:10, ISSUE:4(4)*, 164-170.
7. Boulekbache B, H. M. (2016). Flexural behaviour of steel fiber-reinforced concrete under loading. *Construction building material*, 253-262.
8. Elsaid, A. M. (2011). Mechanical properties of kenaf fiber reinforced concrete. *Construction and Building Materials* 25 (4). Elsevier:1991–2001. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.11.052.
9. Guler, S. a. (2019). Post-cracking behavior of hybrid fiber-reinforced concrete-filled steel tube beams. *Construction and Building Materials* 205 (April). doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.01.192., 285–305.
10. Hasan KMF, H. P. (2020). Potential natural fiber polymeric nanobiocomposites: a review. *Polymers* 2020; 12:, 1072.
11. Hasan, K., Horváth, P., & Alpár, T. (2020). Potential natural fiber polymeric nanobiocomposites: a review. *Polymers* 2020; 12:, 1072.
12. Hasan, K., Wang, H., & Mahmud, S. (2021). Wool functionalization through AgNPs: coloration, antibacterial and wastewater treatment. *Surf Innov* 2021; 9:.
13. ISHAN, A., ATUL, V., MUKESH, K. D., DR, V. R., & SUSANTA, K. S. (2022). A REVIEW PAPER ON PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE WITH JUTE FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETE WITH PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF CEMENT WITH METAKAOLIN. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering - Vol. 7 No. 4 April, 2022*, 897-901.
14. Islam, M. S. (2018). Influence of jute fiber on concrete properties. *Construction and Building Materials* 189 (November):768–76. Elsevier.

- doi:10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2018.09.048.
15. Islam, S. M. (2012). Fiber-reinforced concrete incorporating locally available natural fibers in normal- and high-strength concrete and a performance analysis with steel fiber-reinforced composite concrete. *Journal of Composite Materials* 46 (1):111–22. doi:10.1177/0021998311410492.
 16. Islam, S. M., A., & G. M., S. (2023). Using Jute Fiber to Improve Fresh and Hardened Properties of Concrete. *JOURNAL OF NATURAL FIBERS* 2023, VOL. 20, NO. 2, 2204452, 1-17.
 17. J, S. N., Dr, K. C., Bifathima, D. S., & V, V. K. (2022). Performance on Jute Fiber Reinforced Concrete with Admixtures and the Replacement of Fine Aggregate by Moorum Soil. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*. vol. 04(04). DOI: 10.36948/ijfmr.2022.v04i04.068, 590-595.
 18. J, S. N., Dr, K. C., Dr, N. P., & M, P. (2021). Experimental Investigation on Jute Fibre Concrete with Partial Replacement of Cement with Alccofine and Metakaolin Using M30 Grade of Concrete. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN TECHNOLOGY (IJIRT) | Volume 8 Issue 4 | ISSN: 2349-6002*, 591-594.
 19. Jack, A. C., Muhammad, A., Alireza, T., & D, B. M. (2023). Effects of Fibre Moisture Content on the Mechanical Properties of Jute Reinforced Compressed Earth Composites. *Construction and Building Materials* 373 (2023) 130848 - Elsevier, 1-10.
 20. Khaleel OR, A.-M. S. (2011). The effect of coarse aggregate on fresh and hardened properties of self-compacting concrete (SCC). . Khaleel OR, Al-Mishhadani SA and Abdul Razak H. The effect of coarse agg *Procedia Eng* 2011; 14:, 805-813.
 21. Khan, M. B., Shafiq, N., Waqar, A., Radu, D., Cismaş, C., Imran, M., . . . Benjeddou, O. (2023). Effects of Jute Fiber on Fresh and Hardened Characteristics of Concrete with Environmental Assessment. *buildings*, 1-29.
 22. Khawaja A, T., Jamil, A., Syed, A. H., & Muhammad S, I. (2023). Influence on compressive and tensile strength properties of fiber-reinforced concrete using polypropylene, jute, and coir fiber. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Materials* 2023; 32: 20220263, 1-7.
 23. Ku H, W. H. (2011). A review on the tensile properties of natural fiber reinforced polymer composites. . *Compos B Eng* 2011; 42:, 856-873.
 24. Kundu, S. P. (2012). Chemically modified jute fibre reinforced non-pressure (NP) concrete pipes with improved mechanical properties. . *Construction and Building Materials* 37 (December):841–50. Elsevier. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2012.07.082., 841-850.
 25. Lamees, S. F. (2018). Study of the Mechanical Properties of Jute Fiber Reinforced Cement Composites. . *Engineering and Technology Journal*. Vol. 36, Part A, No. 12, 2018, 1244-1248.
 26. Lasiyal, N., Balot, N. K., Sharma, P., Falwaria, N., & Meena, P. K. (2016). Experimental Study of Concrete Additive Jute as Geotextile Material. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, 1-3.
 27. M, K., G, S., S, R., & I, R. R. (2020). Experimental Investigation on Jute Fibre Reinforced Concrete with Partial Replacement of Fine Aggregate by Plastic Waste. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 981 (2020) 032066. doi:10.1088/1757-899X/981/3/032066, 1-8.

28. Mansur, M. A. (1982). A study of jute fibre reinforced cement composites. . *International Journal of Cement Composites and Lightweight Concrete* 4 (2). Elsevier:75–82. doi:10.1016/0262-5075(82)90011-2, 75-82.
29. MOHAMMAD, M. K., MD, M. I., & HAO, W. (2013). Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Jute Fibre Reinforced Composites. *Journal of Multifunctional Composites*, 71-77.
30. Mohammad, S. I., & Syed, J. A. (2018). Influence of jute fiber on concrete properties. *Construction and Building Materials* 189 (2018) 768–776 - ELSEVIER, 768-776.
31. Mohammad, Z., Mashud, A., Md, M. H., & Islam, S. (2016). Scope of using jute fiber for the reinforcement of concrete material . *Textiles and Clothing Sustainability* (2016) 2:11 - Springer - Open Scsess, 1-10.
32. Mohammadi, Y. S. (2008). Properties of steel fibrous concrete containing mixed fibres in fresh and hardened state. *Construction and Building Materials* 22. Elsevier:95.conbuildmat. 2006.12.004, 56-65.
33. Muhammad Basit Khan, N. S. (2023). Effects of Jute Fiber on Fresh and Hardened Characteristics of Concrete with Environmental Assessment . *Buildings* 2023, 13, 1691, 1-29.
34. Neville, A. M. (2011). *Properties of concrete*. . 5th ed. Essex, England: Pearson Education Limited.
35. Nizamuddin S, J. A. (2019). Synthesis and characterization of polylactide/rice husk hydrochar composite. *Sci Rep* 2019; 9, 5445.
36. Omar, F., Andrzej, K. B., Hans-Peter, F., & Mohini, S. (2012). Biocomposites reinforced with natural fibers: 2000–2010. *Progress in Polymer Science* 37 (2012) - Elsevier, 1552-1596.
37. P, J., & Hariharan. (2019). Study On Concrete With Jute As Admixture And Rubber Asaggregate. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*. Volume: 06 Issue: 05 | May 2019. e-ISSN: 2395-0056, 2429-2434.
38. Pereira ENB, B. J. (2004). Post-cracking behaviour of steel fibre reinforced concrete. . *Mater Struct* 2004; 38, 47–56. .
39. Pramodini Sahu, C. T. (2020). Effect of Jute Fibre Orientation and Percentage on Strength of Jute Fibre Reinforced Concrete . *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT)*, 1767-1770.
40. Pruttipong, P., Warunee, A., Tawatchai, M., Rattiyakorn, S., Ketsara, A., & Hiroyuki, H. (2014). Effect of Modified Jute Fiber on Mechanical Properties of Green Rubber Composite. *11th Eco-Energy and Materials Science and Engineering (11th EMSES)-Elsevier, Energy Procedia*, Vol. 56, 641-647.
41. R, B. A., C, V. S., & B, B. (2019). Dynamic mechanical properties of natural fiber Composites - A Review. *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials - Springer*, 1-22.
42. Ramaswamy, H. S. (1983). Behaviour of concrete reinforced with jute, coir and bamboo fibres. . *International Journal of Cement Composites and Lightweight Concrete* 5 (1).Elsevier:3–13. doi:10.1016/0262-5075(83)90044-1, 3-13.
43. S, Vishwanath, Prof, D. K., & H, P. L. (2017). PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND STRENGTH AUGMENTATION OF CEMENT MORTAR EINFORCED WITH TREATED JUTE FIBRE: A REVIEW. *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 346-352.
44. Sahu, P., & Tudu, C. (2020). Effect of Jute Fibre Orientation and Percentage on Strength of Jute Fibre Reinforced Concrete.

- International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), 1767-1770.
45. SD., S. I. (2016). Evaluating plastic shrinkage and permeability of polypropylene fiber reinforced concrete. . *Int J Sustain Built Environ* 2016; 5:, 345–354.
46. Sivakumaresa, C. L. (2021). Strength and durability characteristics of coir, kenaf and polypropylene fibers reinforced high performance concrete. . *Journal of Natural Fibers* 19 (13):6692–700. doi:10.1080/15440478.2021.192965.
47. Subbiah, A. S. (2021). Experimental investigations to promote better adaptability of safety helmets using jute fiber reinforced Polyester Composites– a Waste Utilization Approach. . Taylor & Francis. doi:10.1080/15440478.2.
48. Sun, J. F. (2021). Electromagnetic absorption of copper fiber oriented composite using 3D printing. . *Construction and Building Materials* 300 (September). Elsevier:124026. doi:10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2021.124026.
49. Sureshkumar, N., Adithya, M., Gayathry, B., Jayasree, S., & Straya, B. (2022). Past Investigations on Strength and Durability Characteristics of Natural Fibre Reinforced Cement Composites with Nano Silica. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT)* Volume 2, Issue 6, June 2022., 916-927.
50. T., R. G. (2005). Impact strength of a few natural fibre reinforced cement mortar slabs: a comparative study. . *Cem Concr Compos* 2005; 27, 547-553.
51. Thanushan K, Y. Y. (2021). Strength and durability characteristics of coconut fibre reinforced Earth cement blocks. *J Nat Fibers* 2021; 18:, 773–788.
52. Ubayi, S. S. (2024). THE TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACT OF ADVANCED STRUCTURAL INNOVATIONS ON ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT. *SANGAM International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. Vol. 01, Issue 02, March, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10939817>, 55-68.
53. Ubayi, S. S., Dr, B. S., Dr, E. A., Shashivendra, D., Umar, S. I., Ibrahim, A. I., & Mustapha, N. G. (2024). Shift From Traditional to Modern Building Concepts and Designs in Ringim Town: A Comparative Stusy of Aesthetics, Values, Functions and Durability. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. Volume 09 Issue 06. ISSN-2456-2165.
54. V., R. K. (2020). Study of structural properties evaluation on coconut fiber ash mixed concrete. . *Mater Today Proc* 2020; 22:, 811–816.
55. Vivek, S., Abhishek, T., & Abhinav, S. (2021). Study of Behavior of Jute Fiber Concrete including Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer Rebar's . *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology - Vol.11, No.4*, 444-446.
56. W., Z. (2020). Permeation properties of self-compaction concrete. In: *Self-compacting concrete: materials, properties and applications*. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2020, 117-130.
57. Yan, L. a. (2013). Compressive and flexural behaviour and theoretical analysis of flax fibre reinforced polymer tube encased coir fibre reinforced concrete composite.

- Materials & Design 52 (December):801–11. Elsevier Ltd.
58. Yang, J. D. (2011). Concrete with recycled concrete aggregate and crushed clay bricks. . Construction and Building Materials 25 (4):19. Elsevier. , 35-45.
59. Yaseen A, S., Nadia N, S., Muhammed F, Y., Ahmed S, A., & Ektiffa S, K. (2019). Concrete Beams Strengthened with Jute Fibers. Civil Engineering Journal, 767-776.
60. Yazici, Ş. G. (2007). Effect of aspect ratio and volume fraction of steel fiber on the mechanical properties of SFRC. Construction and Building Materials. Elsevier:1250–53.
61. Zakaria, M. M. (2020). A comparative study of the mechanical properties of jute fiber and yarn reinforced concrete composites. . Journal of Natural Fibers 17 (5). Taylor and Francis Inc.:676–87., 676-687.
62. Zhou, X. S. (2013). Fracture and Impact Properties of Short Discrete Jute Fibre-Reinforced Cementitious Composites. . Materials & Design 49:35–47. Elsevier Ltd. doi:10.1016/j. matdes.2013.01.029., 35-47.

HOW TO CITE: Salihu Sarki Ubayi, Dr. Esar Ahmad, Dr. Bashir Sabo Abubakar, Shashivendra Dulawat, Mustapha Nuhu Garko, Auwal Ahmad, Umar Shehu Ibrahim, Ibrahim Abdullahi Ibrahim, A Review of the Impact of Jute Fiber Reinforcement on Mechanical Properties of Concrete, Int. J. in Engi. Sci., 2024, Vol 1, Issue 2, 13-34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12670017>

